

Investigation of the patterns of the aerosol loads over Albania

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ABSTRACT

Aerosol load over Albania region was studied in this paper. Principal optical characteristics of aerosols such as aerosol optical depth and Angstrom exponent are used for this purpose. Data are retrieved basically from satellite-based observations. Principal analyses are focused over spatial and temporal distribution of these aerosol parameters, their seasonal and interannual patterns, and fine/coarse mode investigation. The overall results show that western part of Albania has the highest aerosol presence, mainly constituted by fine or mixed aerosol modes. The spring-summer period is characterized by the highest aerosol load.

Key words: Aerosol load, model-satellite data, Albania region

INTRODUCTION

Aerosols play an important role in the air quality and climate variability [1]. Aerosols contribute to the global radiation budget through their direct and indirect effects. Direct effects of aerosols imply their role on scattering-absorbing incoming-outgoing radiation [2], [3]. Meanwhile, aerosol indirect effect or aerosol cloud interactions, modulate the global radiation budget through their modification of the cloud micro-physical and geometrical properties [4]. These implications of the aerosols make them an essential factor on climate change assessments [5]. Aerosol-radiation interactions generally diminish heatwave extremes because of the reduction of the incoming solar radiation. Aerosols can change the properties of clouds, influencing to a large extent the precipitation-forming processes [6]. Their concentrations are highly inhomogeneous, and their role in climate has more regional character [7]. The presence of the aerosols also impacts the human's health [8], [9],[10].

Desert dust, or mineral dust, constitutes the major part of the natural aerosols with 60-200 million of tons per year [11], [12]. Principal sources are the major deserts, such as Sahara, Gobi, Arabian, etc. These events affect mostly the coarse aerosol mode and are of relevant interest for the atmospheric radiative balance [13],[14], [15].

Extreme episodes of aerosol load over the European continent and especially over the Mediterranean region are often related to Saharan dust intrusions [16],[17],[18], [19], [20][21], [22], [23], [14], [24],[25]. Saharan Desert affects also the Balkan Peninsula [26],[27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33]. However, its eastern side, the region in which is situated also Albania, is affected also by the Arabian Desert [25]. Continuous studies regarding atmospheric over the Albanian region have been performed during the last years [34], [35].

The paper consists of the study spatial and temporal distribution of aerosol loads and the special case of two intense dust events.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To investigate dust concentrations, several methodologies may be implied. Among them, the most utilized methods are; in-situ measurements such as in-situ observations, passive and active remote sensing, satellite products, modelling, etc. Thus, the model output may be used in the space regions and time intervals which lack of measurement data.

To investigate dust intrusions over the region of Albania, satellite observations and model databases are used. Satellite observations are provided by the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) <https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/>, on-board of the Aqua and Terra satellites. Moreover, GIOVANNI tool (Earth Data) is used to provide the statistics of the AOD data (<https://giovanni.gsfc.nasa.gov/giovanni/>).

The investigation of the dust intrusions is based on the identification of the variability of their principal optical and microphysical properties; aerosol optical depth (AOD), Angstrom exponent (AE), etc. This study aims to investigate dust intrusions over a 19-year period; February 2000 – February 2019.

EOSDIS Worldview which provide images based on the Corrected Reflectance layer, are used to show the presence of dust plumes over the region under investigation [36].

Furthermore, model products, such are Hybrid Single Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory model – HYSPLIT [37], [38], [39] and Navy Aerosol Analysis Prediction System – NAAPS [40] are engaged in forecasting air mass movement and identification of aerosol sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spatial and temporal distribution of aerosol loads

Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) and Angstrom Exponent (AE) are the principal aerosol optical parameters taken into account in this investigation. AOD₅₅₀ provided by the MODIS, maps the aerosol load distribution over Albania region, give inter-annual trend and seasonal variation of the AOD mean values. AOD₅₅₀ map over the Albanian region is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Time Averaged Map of AOD₅₅₀ and Deep Blue Angstrom Exponent for land (0.412-0.47 micron): Mean of Daily Mean monthly 1 deg. [MODIS-Terra MOD08_M3 v6.1], period Feb2000-Mar2020.

The map of the Fig.1 suggests that the highest aerosol load was found over the southwestern and western parts of Albania (AOD₅₅₀=0.21 and AOD₅₅₀=0.23), associated by the lowest Angstrom Exponent (AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀=1.2 and AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀=1.3). The eastern and northwestern part of Albania has the lowest aerosol load (AOD₅₅₀=0.15) associated by Angstrom Exponent (AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀=1.5 and AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀=1.4). Meanwhile the other parts of the region have intermediate values of AOD. However, the mean values of AOD don't differ too much, because the relatively small area under the investigation. In order to have more insight that the simple total average of AOD₅₅₀, time series of their monthly averaged values and inter-annual variations of their seasonal means are presented in Fig. 2.

a)

b)

Fig. 2. a) Time series of monthly-averaged AOD₅₅₀. b) Inter-annual time series of the seasonal means AOD₅₅₀. Combined Dark Target and Deep Blue for land and ocean; period Feb 2000–Feb 2019

The upper graph of the Fig. 2 suggests a cyclic variation of the mean AOD₅₅₀ over the region. This pattern is investigated further during the seasonal distribution of AOD. The lower graph of the Fig.2 presents inter-annual variation of the regional mean of seasonal AOD₅₅₀ data. Although there are not evidenced any clear trend, a maximum was observed during the period 2007-2008, especially during the summer of 2007. Seasonal maps of AOD₅₅₀ presented in Fig. 3 are used to identify the most affected areas by aerosol load during each season.

Fig. 3 Seasonal distribution of the regional AOD₅₅₀: period DJF (upper-left), JJA (upper-right), MAM (lower-left) and SON (lower-right), 2000-2020. Average Combined Dark Target and Deep Blue AOD at 0.55 micron for land and ocean monthly 1 deg. [MODIS-Terra MOD08_M3 v6.1] for SON months 2000- 2020, Shape Albania

The highest aerosol load in terms of AOD is observed during summer and spring; JJA ($AOD_{550}=0.22\pm 0.30$) and MAM ($AOD_{550}=0.20\pm 0.27$). Much less aerosol loads are observed during the rest of the year; autumn and especially during winter; SON ($AOD_{550}=0.12\pm 0.19$) and DJF ($AOD_{550}=0.03\pm 0.15$).

In order to give more insights over the aerosol types during the aerosol loads, the Angstrom Exponent $AE_{412-470}$ is used. This parameter is higher for fine-mode aerosols and lower for the coarse-mode aerosols. Same, as in Fig. 2.b inter-annual time series of the seasonal means of $AE_{412-470}$ are presented in Fig.4.

Fig. 4 Inter-annual time series of the $AE_{412-470}$. Mean of daily mean 1deg. MODIS-Terra MOD08_M3 v6.1, Feb2000–Mar2020

Fig. 2.b suggests that aerosol load is more intense during MAM-JJA (0.2-0.3), while DJF is the least affected by aerosol load (0.10-0.15). On the other hand, Fig.4 suggests that AE takes the lowest values (1.1-1.4) during the period JJA-MAM. It has got 1.3-1.5 during SON and the highest values (around 1.5) during DJF. Thus, the AOD and AE values are negatively correlated, suggesting that the presence of the coarse mode. The highest aerosol load composed by coarse mode aerosols ($AOD_{550}=0.32$ and $AE_{412-470}=1.05$) during JJA 2017, suggest an intense mineral dust event during that period. However, values of AE higher than 1.0 suggest a mixing state of coarse and fine particles. Thus, the AE values indicate that aerosol isn't pure dust, but mixed with fine mode aerosols, depending on the pathway of the air masses. Mean AE values are almost uniformly distributed over the whole territory. However, during the most active seasons, summer and spring, the southwestern region shows clear lower AE values; 0.3 on JJA and 0.8 in MAM. This fact suggests that this sector is more affected by the coarse mode aerosols compared to the remaining part of Albania (Fig.5).

Fig. 5 Seasonal distribution of the regional $AOD_{412-470}$: period DJF (upper-left), JJA (upper-right), MAM (lower-left) and SON (lower-right), 2000-2020. Average Combined Dark Target and Deep Blue AOD at 0.55 micron for land and ocean monthly 1 deg. [MODIS-Terra MOD08_M3 v6.1] for SON months 2000- 2020, Shape Albania

An overall estimation of the optical characteristics of the aerosols, both AOD and AE, is given also by analysing their statistical distributions.

Fig. 6 Statistical distribution of the AOD₅₅₀ and AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀ values. MODIS-Terra MOD08_M3 V6.1, Feb 2000 – Feb 2019. Statistical data of AOD₅₅₀ ranges in the interval 0.04-0.49, with a mean value of 0.19±0.08 (Fig.6). This is a considerable value, indicating a continuous presence of aerosol load over the region. While, AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀ ranges over the interval 0.01-1.73, with a mean value of 1.35±0.20. This value suggests domination of the fine mode aerosols but also the presence of the mixed phase. The coefficients of variation of AOD₅₅₀ and AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀ are 42.1% and 14.8% respectively. The last result suggests that aerosol optical depth values are more dispersed than those of Angstrom exponent.

Characteristics of the most intense dust events

The most intensive dust events in terms of aerosol optical depth were evidenced tracking information from GIOVANNI. The maxima of AOD₅₅₀ during the entire period 2000-2019 indicate the most intense dust events over the Albania region (Fig.7).

Time Series, Area-Averaged of Combined Dark Target and Deep Blue AOD at 0.55 micron for land and ocean: Mean daily 1 deg. [MODIS-Terra MOD08_D3 v6.1] over 2000-02-24 - 2019-02-01, Region 19.2041E, 39.7046N, 21.0938E, 42.583N

The user-selected region was defined by 19.2041E, 39.7046N, 21.0938E, 42.583N. The data grid also limits the analyzable region to the following bounding points: 19.5E, 40.5N, 20.5E, 42.5N. This analyzable region indicates the spatial limits of the subsetted granules that went into making this visualization result.

Fig. 7 Identification of two of the most intense dust events in terms of AOD₅₅₀; IDE-I and IDE-II.

Annual variation of AOD₅₅₀ during the period with intense events 2002 and 2016, detect the exact time-occurrence of these events. Thus, Fig. 8-9 suggest that the two most intense dust events occur on 13Apr02 (IDE-I) and 23Mar16 (IDE-II).

Fig. 8 Variation of AOD₅₅₀ during the period Jan 2002 – Dec 2002. Identification of the IDE-I.

Fig. 9 Variation of AOD₅₅₀ during the period Jan 2016 – Dec 2016. Identification of the IDE-II. Additionally, images of EOSDIS during these two days are presented in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10 Dust plumes over the area under investigation. a) First intense dust event 13Apr02, b) second intense dust event 23Mar16. MODIS-Terra Corrected Reflectance.

According to the images of Fig.10, in both cases, dust plumes originate from Saharan Desert and enter the Albanian region from its southwestern part. The dust originates in the first event from Libya-Tunisia region, while in the second event dust originate more easterly (Libyan region). The pathways of air masses during these events are more detailed analysed using the HYSPLIT model Fig. 11. a.

As Fig.10 suggested, also Fig.11 show 72hr HYSPLIT back-trajectories of air masses originating over the Libyan-Tunisian region. Furthermore, the NAAPS maps show the intense dust intrusion overpassing the entire Balkan Peninsula coming from Libyan Desert. Despite of this, a significant presence of sulphate over this region is forecasted during the second event. No smoke contamination is forecasted by the NAAPS model for both dust events. According to the HYSPLIT back-trajectories, air masses seem to bring on more dust during the IDE-I compared to the IDE-II. This is justified because while during the IDE-I air masses overpassing Albania at the altitudes 4-6 km pass through Saharan Desert at low altitudes which enabled them to be effective in collecting dust. On the other hand, during the IDE-II, only air masses overpassing Albania at 4 km altitudes can potentially collect dust over Saharan Desert.

In short, main characteristics of IDE-I and IDE-II are respectively as follow; Combined Dark Target and Deep Blue land and ocean (MOD08_M3_V6.1) AOD₅₅₀ both 1.8, Deep Blue Angstrom Exponent for land (MOD08_M3_V6.1) AE₄₁₂₋₄₇₀ 1.8 and 0.9, dust scattering AOT₅₅₀(PM1) from MERRA II are 0.43 and 0.41.

Fig. 11 a) HYSPLIT 72hr back-trajectories and NAAPS maps over Europe during the two intense dust events. a-b) IDE-I and c-d) IDE-II

CONCLUSION

In this paper a study about the dynamics of the variations of the principal aerosol optical parameters over Albania region is presented. Principal aerosol parameters taken into analysis, here are aerosol optical depth and Angstrom exponent.

Southwestern and western regions of Albania are the most affected by aerosol loads. However, the southwestern part was mainly influenced by the coarse mode, while the remaining area is dominated by the fine mode aerosols, or at least by mixed aerosols. No inter-annual trend was observed for AOD and AE values. Moreover, a maximum of AOD was observed during the period 2007-2008. The most active period characterized by higher aerosol loads is the period spring-summer. Maximal values of aerosol load were observed during the summer season (AOD550=0.22±0.30) and spring season (AOD550=0.20±0.27). The significantly lower aerosol load was observed during autumn (AOD550=0.12±0.19) and even less during winter (AOD550=0.03±0.15).

Two intense dust events were detected analysing the AOD data; in April 2002 and March 2016. During these two events, averaged zonal mean AOD550 reached high values as 1.8, whereas dust scattering AOT550(PM1) goes up to 0.4.

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